

French people of Maghreb origin may consider that they already know these norms and consequently, they may think that native French people are no more legitimate than they are, in expressing social control.

In France, the enactment of laws prohibiting the wearing of religious symbols in public spaces created new social norms favoring discrimination. Research in social psychology shows that members of the French majority group are more inclined to "bother" a young Muslim woman who wears the veil than a woman who wears another religious sign. This attitude seems to be legitimized by laws that interfere with the individual's freedom to practice a religion. These laws perceived by Muslims as targeting their religious group, create an ideological context unfavorable to harmonious relations between the different cultural groups in France. The Muslim religion can thus become a criterion for inclusion or exclusion from the national group. While the only wish of young French Muslims is to be perceived as French, they are constantly linked to their religion. For them, this religious group becomes a refuge, a zone of psychological comfort face to discrimination, but also a breeding ground for radicalization.

Recommended readings:

Badea, C., Jetten, J., Iyer, A., & Er-Rafiy, A. (2011). Negotiating dual identities: The impact of group-based rejection on identification and acculturation. *European Journal of Social Psychology, 41*, 586-595.

Nugier, A., Oppin, M., Cohu, M., Kamiejski, R., Roebroek, E., & Guimond, S. (2016). «Nouvelle laïcité» en France et pression normative envers les minorités musulmanes [Secularism in France and normative pressure against Muslim minorities]. *International Review of Social Psychology, 29(1)*.

Oppin, M., Nugier, A., Chekroun, P., & Guimond, S. (2015). Immigrants' generational status affects emotional reactions to informal social control: The role of perceived legitimacy of the source of control. *International Journal of Intercultural Relations, 45*, 1-10.

Authors:

Professor Constantina Badea

bilgierc@bilgi.edu.tr

Phone: 0212 311 5363

